

**Types of Grammatical Metaphors in Harry Potter and the Prisoner of
Azkaban**

Ruzmatova Nigora Nodir qizi

*PhD student of the National university of Uzbekistan named after Mirzo
Ulugbek*

ieltstutor95@gmail.com

I. A. Jurayeva

*Department of Foreign Language and Literature of the National University of
Uzbekistan Ph.D., associate*

Professor iroda70@mail.ru

Abstract

Grammatical Metaphor (GM) is a new language phenomenon established in the framework of functional grammar by Halliday (1985). According to Thompson (2004), the primary source of GM is 'Nominalization,' which occurs when a noun form attempts to represent a verb form, or when a verb form with a distinct process is represented in a noun form. He goes on to say that any phrasing should be metaphorical or consistent. The plot of Harry Potter and the Prisoner of Azkaban was investigated in this study in search of GMs used throughout the first two chapters. This study attempted to uncover occurrences of GM nominalization types in the first two chapters of Harry Potter and the Prisoner of Azkaban and provide solutions. The congruent wordings were then matched to metaphorical wordings to determine the lexical density of each phrasing. Concordance software was used to calculate the lexical density. The study's findings demonstrated, in a very clear way, the advantage of GM in adult writing, which Halliday (1985) claims is one of the notable characteristics of GM. The statistical results demonstrated that the use of GM enhances lexical density, which Halliday (2004) claims is one of the other important aspects of GM. Some consequences for academic writing and reading, as well as for teachers involved, can be made from the findings of this study.

Keywords: Types of Grammatical Metaphors in Harry Potter and the Prisoner of Azkaban

Introduction

Many language studies focus on the link between language and meaning. Indeed, many language researchers have long been fascinated by the interplay between words and meanings, and how they combine to form such a meaningful whole. Based on Halliday's (1985) work, Systemic Functional Linguistics (SFL) addresses this relationship by establishing the idea of Grammatical Metaphor (GM). GM is a phenomenon caused by the stratification of a language's content plane. A language, according to SFL, is a complicated semiotic system with multiple layers (Halliday & Matthiessen, 1999). The content plane of any language, on the other hand, centers around two strata: semantics and lexicogrammar (Yanning, 2008).

The lexicogrammar stratum, which integrates the lexical and grammatical components of language, is concerned with the further translation of meanings into wordings. The semantic stratum is concerned with the transformation of human experience and interpersonal interactions into meanings. According to Halliday and Matthiessen (1999), realization is the link between a language's semantic and lexicogrammatical strata. This realizational link initially appears in patterns where semantic units are congruently mapped onto lexicogrammatical ones as human languages develop. For instance, the grammatical category of clause complex congruently realizes the semantic unit of sequence. The stratified content plane has the capacity to realign the mapping between semantic and lexicogrammatical units, so congruent patterns are not the only form of realization. For instance, a clause or even a group can be used grammatically to represent a semantic unit of sequence rather than a clause complex. The phenomena of GM is this realignment of the connection between semantics and lexicogrammar, as described by Halliday and Matthiessen (1999). In order to help writers, readers, teachers, students, and translators understand language more effectively, researchers hope the current study will shed light on the linguistic knowledge about the grammatical metaphor used in Harry Potter and the Prisoner of Azkaban.

Theoretical Framework

Studies in this area show connections between GM and the ideational, interpersonal, and textual meta-functions of language. The textual meta-function of a text is realized through the management of topic and information systems by GM (Ravelli, 2003). GM As a phenomenon that affects metafunctions and is focused on a particular mode, field, and tenor, GM has gained importance in relation to the contextual analysis of language in use. Additionally, GM is a lexico-grammatical tool that is strongly tied to the three semogenesis processes: phylogenesis, the formation of human language, and individual growth. A deeper understanding of GM within SFL is obtained by theoretical research (Ravelli, 1985; Halliday, 1985; Martin, 1992). According to Halliday and Matthiessen (1999), the two poles of a continuum are, respectively, the congruent and metaphorical expressions of a meaning. To be more precise, a child employs congruent wordings in the early stages of language acquisition. The congruent expression evolves sooner in a language, arises earlier in language development, and appears earlier in a text. Due to the relationship between GM and the three axes of semohistory, GM can be used to compare and describe language use over time (Halliday & Mathiessen 1999). This justification prompts the study to use the SFG approach to analyse the plot of Harry Potter and the Prisoner of Azkaban.

Metaphor

One of the common occurrences in language and literature is metaphor. It has consistently drawn significant interest from a variety of academic fields, including philosophy, psychology, linguistics, and literary studies (Taverniers, 2004). In actuality, a metaphor is a type of movement in which a thing is elevated above itself to become something else (Taverniers, 2004). Following are two examples:

As an example, all senior managers will be fired.

Example 2. He was unaware of it.

According to Tavermiers (2004, p. 4), The use of the 'from...to' statement can be used to describe the metaphorical character of each of these cases. (1) Sweep out, which in literary terms refers to the act of moving something from a certain location, is used to allude to the act of dismissing workers. The word grasp, which is used in example 2,

originally meant to "seize and hold," which is once more a physical activity. However, it is used throughout the instances to relate to grasping an idea. Another way to put it is that a word or lexeme is moved from having a literal meaning to having a figurative meaning in a metaphor.

One term that does have a literal meaning is used to express another word that has a figurative meaning in metaphorical language. Also known as lexical metaphor, this sort of metaphor is seen in these statements. In terms of other semiotic modalities and other linguistic levels, notably the phonological, O'Halloran and Veltman (2000) argue for a broader understanding of metaphor (Ravelli, 2003 as referenced in GM, 2003).

Functional Systemic Linguistics and GM

Halliday produced Systemic Functional Linguistics (SFL) or Systemic Functional Grammar (SFG), a functional theory of language that examines how language functions in human lives (Taverniers, 2004). According to its name, systemic functional linguistics (SFL) views function and semantics as the cornerstones of human language and communicative behaviors (Martin, Matthiessen, & Painter, 1997). Systemic' refers to the idea that language is "a network of systems, or interrelated sets of options for making meaning, and 'functional' refers to the idea that language is what it is because of what it has evolved to do" (Haliday, 1994, p. 15).

Halliday (1984) initially proposed GM against the backdrop of lexical metaphor as one of the several notions introduced in the framework of SFL (Taverniers, 2004). Nominalization, according to Halliday (1985, 1994, & 2003), is the paradigmatic example of GM. They complete their homework is an example of an action that is portrayed in a noun phrase rather than a sentence in GM or nominalization (Painter, 2005). While GM may have first appeared to be a phenomenon on the edge of lexicogrammar for certain readers, it has since evolved into one of the organizing notions connecting lexicogrammar and semantics (Yanning, 2008). The idea of grammatical metaphor, through its anchoring in 'semogenesis' or the evolution of meaning, not only forms an intellectual tool for thinking about the relationship between semantics and grammar, but it also opens the door to a better understanding of the development of language within a culture as well as within individuals and gives us a tool to analyze the genesis and development of meanings in the text. It could be converted into a very

effective instrument for comparative linguistics, translation theory, and related fields, it could be suggested (Yanning, 2008).

Conclusion.

The concept of GM, which was primarily developed by Halliday (1985, 1994), makes a unique and cutting-edge contribution by identifying and describing how literary works—both in writing and in speech—are functionally orientated to achieve the objectification and abstraction of their content. Through the use of GM, a linguistic resource that condenses information by articulating experiences and events in an incongruent form as opposed to the more typical congruent form that predominates in ordinary language use, they are able to attain this functional purpose. The broad and sophisticated use of the nominal group, represented by nominalization, was the main lexico-grammatical element of Harry Potter and the Prisoner of Azkaban. Based on the findings, it was observed that the abundance of GMs in Harry Potter and the Prisoner of Azkaban increased the overall volume of information that the clause or sentence expresses: the more nominalizations that are included, the more information that is expressed by the sentence. The behavioral process was the second most prevalent process type in the current study, and it was also shown that the material process was used more frequently than other processes.

References:

1. Eggins, S. (1994). An introduction to systemic functional linguistics. London: Continuum.
2. Halliday, M.A.K. (1978). Language as a social semiotic. London: Edward Arnold. Halliday, M. A. K. (1985). An introduction to functional grammar. London: Arnold.
3. Halliday, M. A. K.(1989).Spoken and written language. London:Oxford. Halliday, M. A. K.(1998).Things and relations :Re-grammaticising experience as technical knowledge. In JR. Martin & R.Veelceds, Reading science :critical and functional perspectives on discourses of science (pp.185- 235).London:Routledge..
4. Halliday, M. A. K. (1999). New ways of meaning: The challenge to applied Linguistics. In J. Webster (Eds.), (volume 3). London: Continuum.

5. Halliday, M. A. K. (2003). On the architecture of human language. In J. Webster (Eds.), *On Language and Linguistics* (volume 3, pp.123-150). London: Continuum.
6. Arnold. Martin, J.R. (1992). *English Text: System and structure*. Amsterdam: Benjamins.
7. Martin, J. R. , Matthiessen, M. I. M., & Painter, C. (1979). *Working with functional grammar*. New York: Arnold.
8. Painter, C. (2005). The development of language as a resource for learning. In A. Hewings & M. Hewings (Eds.), *Grammar and Context: An Advanced Resource Book*, (pp.183-201). London: Routledge.